

ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF HAEMATOLOGICAL CHANGES IN PREGNANCY RELATED PATHOLOGICAL COMPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Pregnancy induced hematological changes, includes increased blood volume and altered clotting factors, leads to hypercoagulability and potential complications like deep vein thrombosis and preeclampsia. Anaemia occurs due to expanded plasma volume surpassing red blood cell production, elevating risks of preterm birth and maternal fatigue. Platelet count variations affect hemostasis, impacting labor and contributing to bleeding disorders, gradual increase in WBC's indicates presence of infections. The objectives of this study were to evaluate the association between changes in the hematological profile and risks associated with hematological changes in pregnancy related complication. A prospective cohort study at Khurshheed Medical Complex over 8-12 months involved 200 women participants, divided into two groups: first group included 100 pregnant women with pathological complications like anemia, preeclampsia, eclampsia, gestational diabetes, hyperemesis gravidarum and second group included non-pregnant healthy women. Out of 100 pregnant women, anemia was prevalent in 67% of women, gestational diabetes in 13% women, preeclampsia in 9% women, eclampsia in 8% women, and hyperemesis gravidarum in 3% women were also present. Purposive sampling, structured questionnaires covering demographics, pregnancy history, and hematological profiles, along with electronic or paper administration, were employed for data collection. Pregnant women with pathologies (N=100) were compared to non-pregnant healthy women (N=100). Statistical analyses were done using spss v26 and Microsoft Excel. Significant differences were found in hematological indices: Hematocrit $35 \pm 3.17\%$ compared to control group $38.91 \pm 3.67\%$, $P < 0.05$, hemoglobin 9.70 ± 0.99 g/dL compared to control group 11.17 ± 0.95 g/dL, $P < 0.05$, white blood cells and platelets count ($P < 0.05$) was found statistically significant. These findings highlight the importance of dynamic nature of hematological changes during pregnancy. Hematological parameters, including White Blood Cells count, Red Blood Cells count, platelet count, hemoglobin,

hematocrit, Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration, Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin, and Mean Cell Volume, exhibited variations in pregnant women with pathologies compared to non-pregnant healthy women.

INTRODUCTION

World Health Organization (WHO) reported that one woman dies from complications associated with pregnancy. Infection, obstructed labor, eclampsia, hemorrhage during labor and delivery, and unsafe abortion are the leading causes of maternal death. Maternal mortality may be reduced by preventing preventable complications, hence it is crucial to understand the range of the haematological profile during pregnancy and after birth Kaur, Khan, and Nigam (2014). A number of studies have demonstrated a connection between pregnancy-related hypertension and abnormalities in intra- and extracellular water. Hypertensive pregnancy disorders are among the leading causes of morbidity and mortality for both mothers and babies (Pisani et al., 2017).

Alterations and preventative actions are critical in improving the detection of problems and surveillance of underlying illnesses in women during pregnancy, delivery, and the postpartum period. More effort must be put into collecting data and acquiring large reference samples as a result. Not many studies have been done to particularly look at changes in blood cell counts from conception to delivery, even though reference values for maternal health have been established to discourage unnecessary procedures (Soma-Pillay, Nelson-Piercy, Tolppanen, & Mebazaa, 2016). Since pregnant women are not often included in clinical trials and full large-scale cohort data are lacking, our understanding of physiological changes, such as haematological alterations, that may be interpreted as pathogenic in non-pregnant persons is currently restricted (Chakhtoura et al., 2019) Therefore, it is imperative that the characteristics of a healthy pregnancy be thoroughly defined at every stage of the process. The goal is to improve the categorization of high-risk pregnancies and identify unusual patterns of obstetric complications (Patxot et al., 2022).

The laboratory information systems (LIS) derived samples taken from non-pregnant women, which may not be helpful for clinical

choices made during pregnancy. As a result, there is a greater chance that significant physiological changes brought on by pathological circumstances will be missed and that normal changes will be mistaken for diseased ones. For the purpose of accurately evaluating pregnant women in professional settings, it is crucial to comprehend the hematological changes caused by pregnancy (Mutua, Njagi, & Orinda, 2018). Hematological markers play an important part in the emergence of issues by acting as indicators of these adaptive modifications. Pregnancy and its consequences are known to be significantly influenced by the hematological profile (Robinson, Patxot, Stojanov, Blum, & Baud, 2021)

1.11 Objectives

- To evaluate the risks associated with hematological changes in pregnancy related complications such as anemia, thrombocytopenia, or clotting disorders.

- To evaluate the association between the changes in the hematological profile that pregnant women experience and the presence of pathological problems.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

A prospective cohort study of pregnant women at the time of third trimester belonging to different age groups was conducted. The study was 8-12 months long.

3.4 Sample Size

A sample size of 200 females including 100 pregnant women with underlying pathologies like anemia, preeclampsia, eclampsia, gestational diabetes and hyperemesis gravidarum and 100 non-pregnant healthy women were recruited to ensure adequate representation of hematological changes.

3.5 Sampling Technique

The study used a purposive sampling methodology.

3.6 Study Population

Group A: Women with underlying pathological conditions.

3.6.1 Inclusion Criteria

Pregnant patient samples were included (Age \geq 16 years).

Women were recruited during their first trimester (i.e. between 6 to 12 weeks)

(Thangaratinam et al., 2017).

3.6.2 Exclusion Criteria

Women with severe chronic diseases or infectious diseases (e.g., liver disease, urinary system disease, cardiovascular disease, autoimmune disease, hematological disease, AIDS and other diseases before pregnancy)

Hemolyzed samples were excluded and broken vials samples were excluded (Duo, Song, Zhang, et al., 2024).

Group B: Non-pregnant healthy women.

Figure 3.1: Samples collected from pregnant women included in the study

Evaluation of Hematological Parameters:

CBC profile test was performed using Mindray BC-6000 during third trimester for assessing the results of hemoglobin levels, hematocrit, red blood cell indices, white blood cell counts, platelet counts, and other hematological parameters as reported in previous studies. Hematological parameters measured at 6-12 weeks during first trimester, weeks 20-27 during second trimester, 33-37 weeks' during third trimester gestation after the confirmation of the underlying pathologies (Ichipi-Ifukor, Jacobs, Ichipi-Ifukor, & Ewrhe, 2013).

Recording of Results

Results generated by the hematology analyzer were printed out on analyzer slips first and then immediately recorded against the name of every patient to ensure no loss of any results. The report was generated carefully and then clipped into the patient's file (E. I. Obeagu, Hassan, Adepoju, Obeagu, & Okafor, 2021)

Complications Monitoring

Preeclampsia, eclampsia, gestational diabetes, anemia, and hyperemesis gravidarum were some of the pregnancy-related conditions. The

severity as well as the timing of these issues were recorded.

3.11 Data analysis

Data analysis was done using Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) (Version 26 IBM California USA). Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and frequency were calculated first while Chi-square, T-test was used for between group analysis and Anova was performed for within group analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 100 pregnant women were included in this study and out of this 100 pregnant women preeclampsia was present in 9 women, eclampsia was present in 8 women, gestational diabetes was present in 13 pregnant women, anemia was present in 67 women and hyperemesis gravidarum was present 3 in pregnant women. The most common underlying condition, affecting a considerable 67% of the pregnant women, was anemia, a disorder characterized by an insufficient amount of red blood cells or hemoglobin. Fatigue, dyspnea, and other difficulties can

result from anemia during pregnancy in both the mother and the unborn child. Among the women, 13% had gestational diabetes, a kind of the disease that occurs during pregnancy. This highlights the need of blood sugar monitoring throughout pregnancy, particularly for women who have diabetes risk factors (Thanoon et al., 2020).

Preeclampsia, a syndrome marked by elevated blood pressure and possible indications of organ damage, was found to be present in 9% of the pregnant women in this study. 8% of the women had eclampsia, a more serious form of preeclampsia with convulsions. These results emphasize how crucial prenatal care is for blood pressure monitoring and early detection of preeclampsia to avoid consequences. The least prevalent condition, affecting just 3% of

the women was hyperemesis gravidarum, a severe form of nausea and vomiting occurring during pregnancy. Although uncommon, it can be a crippling illness that has a major negative influence on a woman's health throughout her pregnancy. It is noteworthy that the present study did not investigate the causative agents of these illnesses. These disorders can occur because of a variety of factors, including age, weight, family history, and pre-existing medical issues. The statistics illustrates how important prenatal care is. Healthcare professionals may monitor for these issues, take necessary action early on, and apply management methods to maximize pregnancy outcomes with routine checks (Nirupama, Divyashree, Janhavi, Muthukumar, & Ravindra, 2021).

Table 4.1: Distribution of Pregnant Women by Pathological Conditions

Pathologies Present	No of Pregnant Women (N=100)	Percentage
Anemia	67	67%
Gestational Diabetes	13	13%
Pre-eclampsia	9	9%
Eclampsia	8	8%
Hyperemesis Gravidarum	3	3%

Figure 4.1: Complications in Pregnant Women

Out of 100 pregnant women preeclampsia was present in 9% women. Figure below shows the prevalence of preeclampsia

Figure 4.2: Presence of Pre-eclampsia in Pregnant Women

Out of 100 pregnant women 8% women were suffering from eclampsia. Figure below shows the prevalence of eclampsia.

Figure 4.3: Presence of Eclampsia in Pregnant Women

Out of 100 pregnant women 67% women had anemia. Figure shows the prevalence of anemia in pregnant women.

Figure 4.4: Presence of Anemia in Pregnant Women

Out of 100 pregnant women gestational diabetes was found in 13% of pregnant women. Figure below shows the prevalence of gestational diabetes.

Figure 4.5: Shows presence of Gestational Diabetes in Pregnant Women

Out of 100 pregnant women gestational diabetes was found in 3% pregnant women. Figure shows the prevalence of gestational diabetes in pregnant women.

Figure 4.6: presence of Hyperemesis Gravidarum in Pregnant Women

4.2.2 Age group distribution of participants

Table 4.2: Age Distribution of Participants (N=200)

Age Group	Case Group		Control Group	
	No	%	No	%
<=20	13	13%	11	11%
21-30 years	54	54%	47	47%
31-40 years	33	33%	42	42%
Total	100	100%	100	100%

Figure 4.7: Age Distribution of Study Participants

Body Mass Index (BMI) of Participants (Mean)

Figure 4.8: BMI of Participants

Height of the study Participants

Table 4.3: Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristics of Participants	Pregnant Women with Underlying Pathologies (n=100)	Non-pregnant Healthy Women (n=100)
Age (Years)	27.64±5.753	27.64±3.812
Height (meters)	1.5962±0.9042	1.6146±0.3437
Weight (kilograms)	65.1537±8.1736	58.4321±4.8719
BMI	22.5577±2.7994	21.4423±2.7615

Table 4.4: Comparison of Hematological Indices between Two Groups using Independent Sample t-test

Parameters	Case Group Mean±S.D	Control Group Mean±S.D	t-value	Sig. (Two Tailed)
Hb	9.7043±1.2	11.1730±0.95	10.643	<.001
MCHC	30.34±2.24	33.22±2.49	8.502	<.001
MCH	28.60±2.02	32.30±2.03	8.766	<.001
MCV	92.47±6.67	82.38±3.34	9.77	.027
HCT	35.59±2.08	39.92±3.678	6.83	<.001
PLT Count (Thousand/microliter)	151.20±27.25	178.88±29.33	24.339	.020
RBCs Count (Million/Microliter)	3.94±1.06	4.033±2.1478	3.850	<.001
WBCs Count (Thousand/Microliter)	6.38±2.33	5.55±1.53	-2.388	.018
Neutrophils Count (%)	55.95±9.97	42.71±4.67	3.452	.016
Eosinophils Count (%)	4.35±0.81	5.52±1.97	4.553	<.001
ESR	56.05±10.25	24.42±4.41	-2.444	<.001
Lymphocytes Count (%)	39.02±6.67	26.62±4.91	-5.5950	<.001

Monocytes Count (%)	3.49±0.79	3.68±1.96	-7.776	.438
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Table 4.5: Complete Blood Count Indices between two groups, Non-Pregnant Healthy Women and Pregnant Women with Underlying Pathologies using Chi Square test for each parameter

Parameter Name	Control Group (N)	Case Group (N)	X ²	Sig.
Hb				
Low	60	95	24.175	.001
Normal	40	5		
High	0	0		
MCHC				
Low	7	50	45.469	.001
Normal	82	2		
High	11	48		
MCH				
Low	2	18	12.481	.001
Normal	96	42		
High	2	40		
MCV				
Low	17	11	9.74	.001
Normal	82	78		
High	1	11		
Hematocrit				
Low	14	48	27.145	.001
Normal	85	51		
High	1	1		
Platelet Count				
(Thousand/microliter)	8	38	7.675	.001
Low	91	62		
Normal	1	0		
High				
RBCs Count				
(Million/Microliter)	57	68	1.025	.001
Low	43	32		
High				
WBCs Count				
(Thousand/Microlite)	98	42	2.020	.001
Normal	2	58		
High				
Eosinophils Count (%)				
Low	69	52	13.530	.001
High	31	48		
Erythrocyte				

sedimentation Rate	73	1	14.342	.001
Low	27	99		
High				
Lymphocytes Count (%)			41.103	.001
Low	8	3		
Normal	79	41		
High	13	56		
Monocytes Count (%)	4	6	13.542	.482
Low	96	93		
Normal	0	1		
High				

Table 4.5: shows mean haematological parameters between pregnant and non-pregnant women where difference in hemoglobin concentration, PCV, WBC, Eosinophil, Lymphocyte and ESR were found to be statistically significant (p<0.05).

Table 4.6: Comparison of Complete Blood Count over all three Trimesters in Pregnant Women with underlying pathologies

Parameters	1 st Trimester	2 nd Trimester	3 rd Trimester	P value		
Hemoglobin Mean	9.7043±1.2	9.72±1.3	9.71±1.4	NS	NS	NS
Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration Mean	30.34±2.24	30.06±2.43	30.08±2.47	NS	NS	NS
Corpuscular Hemoglobin Mean	28.60±2.02	28.62±2.21	28.91±2.08	NS	NS	NS
Corpuscular Hemoglobin Mean	92.47±6.67	93.41±6.61	93.45±6.69			
Hematocrit	35.59±2.08	35.62±2.6	35.88±2.19	NS	NS	NS
Platelet Count (Thousand/microliter)	151.20±27.25	151.22±10.29	151.61±10.81	NS	NS	NS
Red Blood Cells Count (Million/Microliter)	3.94±1.06	3.96±1.21	3.97±1.23	NS	NS	NS
White Blood Cells Count (Thousand/Microliter)	6.38±2.33	6.39±2.54	6.41±2.59	NS	NS	NS
Neutrophils Count (%)	55.95±9.97	55.91±9.91	55.99±10.34	NS	NS	NS
Eosinophils Count (%)	4.35±0.81	4.42±0.91	4.41±0.88	NS	NS	NS
Erythrocyte sedimentation Rate	56.05±10.25	57.66±10.98	57.98±11.20	NS	NS	NS
Lymphocytes Count (%)	39.02±6.67	39.92±6.82	39.81±6.33	NS	NS	NS
Monocytes Count (%)	3.49±0.79	3.50±0.83	3.53±0.33	NS	NS	NS

Table 4.6: The mean haematological parameters were compared among three trimesters of pregnancy using One Way Anova. All the values were compared with each other between trimesters and none of the parameters were found to be statistically significant.

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

The study aimed to compare the hematological changes of pregnant women with underlying

pathologies and non-pregnant healthy women, participants were divided into two groups: Group A (50%, n=100) and Group B (50%, n=100) respectively. Test results were collected

after running participant's samples on Hematology Analyzer. After clinical examination by an authorized gynecologist and doctor's prescription, all participants were tested for hematological changes. Test results of Complete Blood Count were noted for each participant. The mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, corpuscular volume, hematocrit, platelet count, red blood cell count, white blood cell count, neutrophils count, eosinophils count, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, lymphocytes count, and monocytes count were compared. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was used to access the normality of data, and all parameters were normally distributed.

The comparison of hematological parameters between the two groups using independent sample t-test and within group analysis using One-Way Anova showed significant differences between the two groups' values. Pregnancy-related pathologies were present in pregnant women, including pre-eclampsia, eclampsia, gestational diabetes, anemia, and hyperemesis gravidarum. The complete blood count Indices between the two groups were compared to check association using Chi Square test for each parameter. The results showed the statistical significance between two groups' values. In conclusion, the study provides valuable insights into the hematological changes of pregnant women with underlying pathologies and the importance of addressing these issues during pregnancy.

5.1 Findings

The changes in hematological changes due to pathologies are of significance and these have reported due to poor diet plan and poor management of pregnancy over the course of three trimesters. Pregnancy related pathologies such as preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, and hyperemesis gravidarum and placenta previa frequently exhibit hematological abnormalities like anemia, thrombocytopenia, and leukopenia. The severity of pregnancy-related diseases and the degree of hematological alterations were revealed to be significantly correlated by the study. Anemia has been linked to a higher chance of low birth weight and premature delivery. Thrombocytopenia has been associated with an increased risk of

postpartum hemorrhage and placental abruption. A higher risk of infections in both the mother and the fetus has been linked to leukopenia.

5.2 Conclusion

This study showed hematological changes play a crucial role in the development and progression of pregnancy related pathologies. In particular, women with pre-existing medical illnesses or risk factors should have regular hematological monitoring during their pregnancy, according to the research. Biomarkers indicating the likelihood of pregnancy-related problems might include anemia, thrombocytopenia, and leukopenia. In order to avoid or lessen pregnancy-related diseases, the results show that early detection and control of hematological alterations are essential. Investigations into the fundamental processes via which hematological alterations give rise to pregnancy-associated disorders are necessary in order to create focused treatments. The findings of the study indicate the value of multidisciplinary treatment and teamwork among obstetricians, hematologists, and other healthcare professionals, with implications for clinical practice. Among these pathologies the outcomes of preeclampsia that later on resulted in eclampsia were more complicated that resulted in haemodilution, hem concentration, anemia most importantly, decrease in red blood cells count due to their destruction and at last thrombocytopenia. These resulted in persistent nausea, vomiting, blurry vision, convulsions and high blood pressure. Anemia also caused a lot of issues in pregnant women as the ratio remained at peak in pregnant women it was due to iron deficiency and vitamin B-12 deficiency.

5.4 Recommendations

- To detect such pathologies early, routine hematological monitoring is advised for pregnant mothers, particularly those with risk factors or pre-existing medical illnesses.
- Pregnancy-related diseases may be prevented or reduced with prompt intervention and control of hematological alterations. To increase knowledge and enhance patient care,

hematologists, obstetricians, and other healthcare professionals must work together.

- To further understand the underlying processes, create innovative treatment approaches, and examine the advantages of hematological monitoring in averting problems, more study is required.
- It is important to inform expectant mothers about the possible hazards connected with hematological alterations as well as the significance of hematological monitoring.
- It is necessary to produce evidence-based guidelines for the therapy of hematological alterations in diseases associated with pregnancy.

5.4.1 Future Recommendation

- Employ point-of-care diagnostics that, in clinical settings, can quickly and reliably identify hematological abnormalities and forecast pregnancy-related diseases.
- Examine the connection between recurrent pregnancy loss and hematological alterations, taking into account the possible influence of thrombophilia and other hematological abnormalities.
- Develop risk prediction models to support clinical decision-making by predicting the likelihood of pregnancy-related diseases based on hematological indicators and other risk variables.

REFERENCES

Agarwal, A. M., & Rets, A. (2021). Laboratory approach to investigation of anemia in pregnancy. *International Journal of Laboratory Hematology*, 43, 65-70.

Ali, B. R., & Hameed, R. R. (2022). The Role of Hematological Parameters in Different Trimesters of Pregnancy. *University of Thi-Qar Journal Of Medicine*, 24(2), 104-111.

Amriddinovna, S. S., Shoxrux, M., Amir, N., & Javlonbek, N. (2024). Determination Of Hematological Parameters (Hemogram and Leukogram) In Blood Serum in Women with Generalized Periodontitis, Whose Pregnancy Is Complicated by Iron Deficiency Anemia. *Diversity Research: Journal of Analysis and Trends*, 2(1), 1-4.

Chakhtoura, N., Chinn, J. J., Grantz, K. L., Eisenberg, E., Dickerson, S. A., Lamar, C., & Bianchi, D. W. (2019). Importance of research in reducing maternal morbidity and mortality rates. *American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 221(3), 179-182.

Cobo, T., Kacerovsky, M., & Jacobsson, B. (2020). Risk factors for spontaneous preterm delivery. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 150(1), 17-23.

Dockree, S., Brook, J., James, T., Shine, B., Impey, L., & Vatish, M. (2021). Pregnancy-specific reference intervals for C-reactive protein improve diagnostic accuracy for infection: a longitudinal study. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 517(12), 81-85.

Dockree, S., Shine, B., Pavord, S., Impey, L., & Vatish, M. (2021). White blood cells in pregnancy: reference intervals for before and after delivery. *EBioMedicine*, 74(06), 199-204.

Duo, Y., Song, S., Qiao, X., Zhang, Y., Xu, J., Zhang, J., . . . Sun, Q. (2024). The Association of Hematological Parameters in Early and Middle Pregnancy with the Risk of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity* 13(07), 633-646.

Duo, Y., Song, S., Zhang, Y., Qiao, X., Xu, J., Zhang, J., . . . Sun, Q. (2024). Relationship between serum uric acid in early pregnancy and gestational diabetes mellitus: a prospective cohort study. *Endocrine*, 83(3), 636-647.

Ejike, B., Ukpai, O., Ihemanna, C., Ajuga, M., & Eme, G. (2022). Impact of Malaria infection on the Haematological profile of Pregnant Women in South-Eastern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology* 43(1), 123-127.

- Eledo, B., Buseri, F., & Akhogba, A. (2015). Evaluation of some haematological parameters among pregnant Ijaw women: An indigenous West African tribe. *Evaluation*, 13(03), 145-149.
- He, W. R., & Wei, H. (2020). Maternal and fetal complications associated with systemic lupus erythematosus: an updated meta-analysis of the most recent studies (2017-2019). *Medicine*, 99(16), e197-199.
- Hurrell, A., Webster, L., Chappell, L. C., & Shennan, A. H. (2022). The assessment of blood pressure in pregnant women: pitfalls and novel approaches. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 226(2), S804-S818.
- Ichipi-Ifukor, P. C., Jacobs, J., Ichipi-Ifukor, R. N., & Ewrhe, O. L. (2013). Changes in haematological indices in normal pregnancy. *Physiology Journal*, 2013, 12(03), 132-136.
- Jia, J., Yang, Y., Zhang, M., Lin, L., Chen, Y., Guo, T., Guo, C. (2021). Red Blood Cells in The First Trimester and The Risk of Gestational Diabetes: A Prospective Cohort Study. *International Journal on Obstetrics*, 12(06), 165-169.
- Jung, E., Romero, R., Yeo, L., Gomez-Lopez, N., Chaemsathong, P., Jaovisidha, A., Erez, O. (2022). The etiology of preeclampsia. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 226(2), S844-S866.
- Jung, E. J., Cho, H. J., Byun, J. M., Jeong, D. H., Lee, K. B., Sung, M. S., Kim, Y. N. (2018). Placental pathologic changes and perinatal outcomes in placenta previa. *Placenta*, 63(12), 15-20.
- Kazma, J. M., van den Anker, J., Allegaert, K., Dallmann, A., & Ahmadzia, H. K. (2020). Anatomical and physiological alterations of pregnancy. *Journal of pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics*, 47(4), 271-285.
- Kepley, J. M., Bates, K., & Mohiuddin, S. S. (2023). Physiology, maternal changes. In *StatPearls [Internet]*: StatPearls Publishing. *Journal of Maternal Care*, 19(02), 191-195.
- Khamees, M. H., Wadaha, H. A., & Meshay, H. D. (2021). Changes in hematological and coagulation parameters in women with pregnancy induced hypertension and preeclampsia: Case control study. *Al-Qadisiyah Medical Journal*, 17(1), 1-7.
- Khezri, R., Salarilak, S., & Jahanian, S. (2023). The association between maternal anemia during pregnancy and preterm birth. *Clinical Nutrition ESPEN*, 56(19), 13-17.
- Kjeldgaard, H. K., Vikanes, Å., Benth, J. Š., Junge, C., Garthus-Niegel, S., & Eberhard-Gran, M. (2019). The association between the degree of nausea in pregnancy and subsequent posttraumatic stress. *Archives of women's mental health*, 22(12), 493-501.
- Lassila, R., & Weisel, J. W. (2023). Role of red blood cells in clinically relevant bleeding tendencies and complications. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 21(11), 3024-3032.
- Leal, C. R. V., Costa, L. B., Ferreira, G. C., de Melo Ferreira, A., Reis, F. M., & e Silva, A. C. S. (2022). Renin-angiotensin system in normal pregnancy and in preeclampsia: A comprehensive review. *Pregnancy Hypertension*, 28(13), 15-20.
- Liu, W., Lou, X., Zhang, Z., Chai, Y., & Yu, Q. (2021). Association of neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio, platelet to lymphocyte ratio, mean platelet volume with the risk of gestational diabetes mellitus. *Gynecological Endocrinology*, 37(2), 105-107.
- Nirupama, R., Divyashree, S., Janhavi, P., Muthukumar, S., & Ravindra, P. (2021). Preeclampsia: Pathophysiology and management. *Journal of Gynecology Obstetrics and Human Reproduction*, 50(2), 101975.
- Nooh, A. M., & Abdeldayem, H. M. (2015). Changes in platelet indices during pregnancy as potential markers for prediction of preeclampsia development. *Open Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 5(12), 703-712.

- Obeagu, E., Adepoju, O. J., Okafor, C. J., Obeagu, G. U., Ibekwe, A. M., Okpala, P. U., & Agu, C. C. (2021). Assessment of Haematological Changes in Pregnant Women of Ido, Ondo State, Nigeria. *J Res Med Dent Sci*, 9(4), 145-148.
- Obeagu, E., Anyanwu, C., & Obeagu, G. (2024). Challenges and Considerations in Managing Blood Transfusion for Individuals with HIV. *Elite Journal of HIV*, 2(2), 1-7.
- Obeagu, E., & Obeagu, G. (2024). Understanding Hematocrit Fluctuations in HIV-Malaria Coinfection for Improved Management. *Elite Journal of Public Health*, 2(1), 22-34.
- Obeagu, E. I., Hassan, A., Adepoju, O. J., Obeagu, G. U., & Okafor, C. J. (2021). Evaluation of Changes in Haematological Parameters of Pregnant Women Based on Gestational Age at Olorunsogo Road Area of Ido, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Medical and Dental Science*, 9(12), 462-464.
- Örgül, G., Haklı, D. A., Özten, G., Fadiloğlu, E., Tanacan, A., & Beksaç, M. S. (2019). First trimester complete blood cell indices in early and late onset preeclampsia. *Turkish Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 16(2), 112.
- Osmundson, S. S., Zhao, B. S., Kunz, L., Wang, E., Popat, R., Nimbale, V. C., & Palaniappan, L. P. (2016). First trimester hemoglobin A1c prediction of gestational diabetes. *American Journal of Perinatology* 312(09), 977-982.
- Palma dos Reis, C. R., Cardoso, G., Carvalho, C., Nogueira, I., Borges, A., & Serrano, F. (2020). Prediction of adverse pregnancy outcomes in women with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Clinical Reviews in Allergy & Immunology*, 59(3), 287-294.
- Patel, P., & Balanchivadze, N. (2021). Hematologic findings in pregnancy: a guide for the internist. *Cureus*, 13(5), 190-199.
- Patxot, M., Stojanov, M., Ojavee, S. E., Gobert, R. P., Kutalik, Z., Gavillet, M., . . . Robinson, M. R. (2022). Haematological changes from conception to childbirth: An indicator of major pregnancy complications. *European Journal of Haematology*, 109(5), 566-575.
- Pham, H. N., Huynh, N. X., Pham, P. N. H., Dang, D. N. Y., Cao, L. T., Huynh, D. M., . . . Beaupha, S. M. C. (2023). Reference intervals of complete blood count and coagulation tests in Vietnamese pregnant women. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 23(1), 788-798.
- Pisani, I., Tiralongo, G., Presti, D. L., Gagliardi, G., Farsetti, D., Vasapollo, B., . . . Valensise, H. (2017). Correlation between maternal body composition and haemodynamic changes in pregnancy: different profiles for different hypertensive disorders. *Pregnancy hypertension*, 10(03), 131-134.
- Robinson, M. R., Patxot, M., Stojanov, M., Blum, S., & Baud, D. (2021). Postpartum hemorrhage risk is driven by changes in blood composition through pregnancy. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 19238.
- Soma-Pillay, P., Nelson-Piercy, C., Tolppanen, H., & Mebazaa, A. (2016). Physiological changes in pregnancy: review articles. *Cardiovascular journal of Africa*, 27(2), 89-94.
- Stoikou, M., Grimolizzi, F., Giaglis, S., Schäfer, G., van Breda, S. V., Hoesli, I. M., Rossi, S.
- Thangaratnam, S., Allotey, J., Marlin, N., Mol, B. W., Von Dadelszen, P., Ganzevoort, W., Deeks, J. (2017). Development and validation of Prediction models for Risks of complications in Early-onset Preeclampsia (PREP): a prospective cohort study. *Health technology assessment*, 21(18), 130.
- Thanoon, A. H., Sultan, A. S., & Hameed, B. H. (2020). Maternal hematological profile from the first to third trimester of pregnancy in normal pregnant Iraqi women. *Plant Arch*, 2(20), 6528-6532.